

DEVELOPMENT OF STRENGTH QUALITIES OF YOUNG STUDENTS IN ATHLETICS

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Annotation: *It was noted that the dynamics of physical formation and physical training of a person depend on the level of the student's ability to work, as well as the nature and size of regular exercises. Currently, there is a lot of information about the effect of excessive physical load on the body of athletes, but there are many cases of giving students the same loads without taking into account the characteristics of the body of young students. Due to this, proper planning of the training process is in accordance with the purpose.*

Key words: Strength, ability, skill, exercise, training.

Аннотация: *Отмечено, что динамика физического формирования и физической подготовленности человека зависит от уровня трудоспособности студента, а также характера и размера регулярных занятий. В настоящее время имеется много информации о влиянии чрезмерных физических нагрузок на организм спортсменов, однако немало случаев предоставления студентам одинаковых нагрузок без учета особенностей организма студенческой молодежи. Благодаря этому правильное планирование тренировочного процесса соответствует цели.*

Ключевые слова: Сила, способность, умение, упражнение, тренировка.

Anotatsiya: *Shaxsning jismoniy shakllanishi va jismoniy tayyorgarlik dinamikasi o'quvchining mexnat qila olish qobiliyati darajasi xamda doimiy bajariladigan mashqlar xarakteri va xajmiga bog'liqdir deb ta'kidlashgan. Hozirgi vaqtda sportchilar organizmiga ortiqcha jismoniy yuklama qanday ta'sir ko'rsatishi bo'yicha katta ma'lumotlar to'plangan bo'lsada, o'quvchi yoshlar organizmi xususiyatlarini xisobga olmasdan, ularga bir xildagi yuklamalar berish hollari xam ko'p uchraydi. Shu tufayli mashg'ulot jarayonini tug'ri rejalashtirish maksadga muvofiqdir.*

Kalit so'zlar: Kuch, qobiliyat, maxorat, mashq, trenirovka.

Speed of movement and endurance and agility largely depend on muscle strength. Muscle strength depends on the state of the central nervous system corresponding to the activity of the cerebral cortex, the physiological cross-section of muscles, biochemical processes in muscles, changes in muscle excitability, their fatigue level and other reasons. muscle strength occurs only when the impulses from the nerve tissues of the motor zone in the cerebral cortex arrive. This shows that the functional capabilities of the nervous system are of decisive importance.

The development of muscle strength, especially in novice athletes, is first of all due to the ability to control their muscles, to be able to shorten them and to strengthen them with more force (improve neuromuscular coordination). At the same time, it is important to learn how to show great will power. In addition, the ability to show muscle strength is developed by increasing the functional capacity of nervous tissue. Since muscle strength is directly proportional to its physiological cross-section, as muscle mass increases under the influence of physical exercise, muscle strength also increases, at the same time, muscle circulation increases, metabolism improves, energy-giving substances increases. These main aspects of muscle strength are interrelated. However, it is possible to choose exercises and methods that increase the muscle mass more or increase the level of the appropriate functional capabilities of the nervous tissue and improve the ability to show strength.

Cultivating qualities of strength and speed. In modern sports practice, the quality of strength is of incomparable importance. No matter what movement an athlete does (running, jumping, throwing, etc.), the effectiveness of this movement is related to strength.

All muscles in the body of young athletes should be strong and harmoniously developed. But the demand for the level of development of body muscles depends on the type of athletics. Throwers need more strength to develop than others, while marathoners need less strength than others.

Any athlete in training is definitely a strength developer exercises. But mainly attention is paid to the development of the most important muscle group for performing this type of athletics.

A variety of dynamic exercises are used to develop strength, from elemental exercises to complete athletics (jumping, throwing, jumping). Weight lifting exercises, exercises performed using one's own weight or overcoming the resistance of a partner are the most useful for developing strength.

Exercises performed with a heavy load, for example, with a barbell, are for the whole body muscles, especially large and strong muscle groups, and exercises

performed with light loads (for example, exercise balls, dumbbells) affect some muscle groups.

When an athlete is exercising with a very heavy load, he sometimes breaks his breathing rhythm or stops breathing completely. It is necessary to pay great attention to proper breathing, perform the exercises with maximum weight only once, and spend 25 minutes before starting the next one.

The exercise performed with a light load should be repeated 23 times in a row (sometimes less). The smaller the weight, the more you can do the exercise without stopping. Exercises performed to increase muscle size should always be repeated until fatigue is felt in the muscles.

It is recommended to perform weight-bearing exercises slowly at first, then as fast as the weight allows.

Throwing equipment heavier than weight-bearing athletic exercises in training, jumping with a bag filled with sand (6-12 kg) on the shoulder, jumping up with a heavy (5-6 kg) belt exercises are also used. In such exercises, the structure of the movement does not change, but the athlete has to spend more effort than usual. Strength develops in conditions close to the conditions necessary for an athlete.

Beginner athletes should do a variety of physical exercises to develop all the muscles in the body. Well-trained athletes should develop those muscle groups that require them to be strong in order to succeed in their chosen sport. Of course, they should maintain their general fitness levels with strength-building exercises.

In conclusion, exercises that increase strength are used more during the preparation period of the training, and less often during the competition. But during the competition, special exercises (which often require maximum effort) are left enough. This is necessary not only to maintain the level achieved in the development of strength, but also to increase it further. In forming their physical qualities, it is important to pay special attention to the exercises that have the "power" to effectively develop their fitness and are suitable for the characteristics and coordination of gymnastic elements.

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